

BUILDING A SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS AND ITS ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Bozorboyeva Diyora

Bonu Shodlik daughter

Student of Urganch State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7751823>

ABSTRACT: Entrepreneurial activity is analyzed in terms of its influence on the stability of the development of the entrepreneurial environment. The mechanism of the impact of entrepreneurship on development stability is considered, the presence of three opposing sides, interaction and interdependence, which make up the system that guarantees development stability, is shown.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, business environment, stability, sustainable development.

System development requires stability to realize an upward trajectory. Regardless of what radical shifts occur, qualitative stability prevents the system from going outside the "cone of acceptance" and prevents large losses and unexpected disruptions. As the system reaches a higher level, the limits of development expand, increasing its agility and flexibility. Modern approaches to evaluating the development of the economic system include the study of stability as a prerequisite for the competitiveness of the business environment. Determining the essence of sustainability has attracted the attention of scientists and major organizations, but they have not yet reached a consensus. In addition to the topics,

In the course of research, it was determined that not only stability is a necessary condition for the development of entrepreneurship, but also that stability depends on the quality of entrepreneurial activity and its intensity. Stability is a key condition for the region's competitiveness, which is proven by concepts dating back to the 1970s, particularly the popular theories of "limits to growth" and "sustainable growth". The main ideas about this social structure were first expressed in full form by L. Brown in his work "Building a Sustainable Society".

In the resolution of the UN conference in Rio de Janeiro (1992), sustainable development was defined as development that meets the needs of the present, but does not meet the needs of the present, and the ability of future generations to meet their own needs is at risk. The report also states that it is aimed at the fair distribution of resources between and within generations, so that there is a current agreement and deferred consumption. In other words, the growth rate of consumption in the future should not exceed the growth rate of capital productivity, that is, production efficiency. The classic conclusion is that researchers of this question,

the maximum level of replacement of individuals should be equal to the total return on investment relative to consumption in subsequent periods. Giving up current consumption for the purpose of consuming a large amount of goods in the future can be seen as an investment.

The authors of the book "Blueprint for a Sustainable" Economy "D. Pierce and E. Berbil define sustainability from an economic point of view" under "capital" as "irreducible capital", not only financial capital or human capital, as it is customary to interpret it in traditional

economics and "natural capital" as follows: the land itself is valuable to people. In the most general form, the stability of the economic system is defined as the ability to relatively quickly return to the original situation or to reach a new, higher level, points on the development trajectory.

The difference of scientific research in the creation of concepts of "sustainability" is explained by the use of principles and rules expressed in developments of an integral nature. During the genesis of the analyzed concept, attempts were made not only to emphasize the main "sustainable development" trends, but also to find out the reasons that cause this phenomenon. Thus, R. Norgard believes that it is necessary for a new understanding of the environment, technology, social organization, knowledge, value-forming systems and their interaction.

Ideally, sustainable development is a continuous wave of internal and external environmental restructuring aimed at ensuring consistent, long-term balanced operation of the organization. Stability means the presence of certain fluctuations, which, nevertheless, allow the system to maintain an important invariant, i.e. does not change, does not threaten its main feature, ratio, limitation, subsystem, element, what is immanently the main, essential aspect of existence. Sustainable development implies the goal of consistent improvement without destroying the integrity of the system, which includes the ability to change the distortions of quality growth systems. According to our understanding, sustainable development is the integration of economic, political, social and environmental spheres.

The phenomenon of system stability considered in relation to economic systems, it is a basic feature of nature and social dynamic systems. For the former, the appearance, stability means permanence, the invariance of a certain state of the system. But stability in the economic sense is the stability of movement in a certain direction, the advantages of maintaining and developing the main competitors.

We believe that entrepreneurship is a key determinant of this sustainability. Sustainability and entrepreneurship are naturally interrelated. Sustainability is a necessary but not sufficient condition for the development of an entrepreneurial environment. Business activity is a necessary but not sufficient condition for sustainable development and growth. The interaction between the two components ensures the stability, growth and development of the system.

Entrepreneurship is important for the impact of the entrepreneurial environment on the stability of socio-economic development at the regional level, first of all, the ability to neutralize the negative effects of the associated negative things, and secondly, the ability to ensure a continuous reproductive process.

References:

1. Brown LR Building a sustainable society / LR Brown. - New York ; London: Norton, 1981. - 433 p.
2. Story of the world in the 21st century: OON po conference okhrane okrujayushchey srede i razvitiyu. Rio de Janeiro, July 1992. Izrecheniya. - M. : Tsentr koordinatsii i sotsialno-ekonomicheskogo soyuza, 1997. - 218 p.
3. Pierce D. Plan of sustainable economy / D. Pierce, E. Barbier. - London: Earthscan, 2000. - 273 p.

4. Kalinchikov M. Yu. Teoretiko-metodicheskie osnovy kontseptsii ustoychivogo razvitiya regiona / M. Yu. Kalinchikov // Economy in the region. – 2005. – No. 9.
5. Norgaard RB Sustainable Development:RB Norgaard / / Futures. – 1988. – No. 20 (6).

